

NITRATION OF SOME SULPHIDES OF ORGANIC COMPOUNDS AND REDUCTION OF THEIR NITRO PRODUCTS

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Nitration of 2:2'-dibenzoyldinaphthyl sulphide, 3:3'-dicarbomethoxy-4:4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide, and 3:3'-dicarbomethoxy-4:4'-diacetoxydiphenyl sulphide has been carried out and the nitro products obtained have been reduced.

Nitration of 2:2'-dibenzoyldinaphthyl sulphide gives a dinitro derivative which yields on hydrolysis 2:2'-dihydroxy-5:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide, identical with the compound reported earlier (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 211). On reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid, the nitro groups are reduced and the sulphur linkage broken, but with zinc dust, ammonium chloride and alcohol (Morgan and Micklethwait, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 151) reduction without breaking of sulphur linkage and debenzoylation takes place.

On similar nitration 3:3'-dicarbomethoxy-1:4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide gives a mixture of two nitro derivatives, one with sulphur and the other, without sulphur, the former being 3:3'-carbomethoxy-1:4'-dihydroxy-5:5'-dinitrodiphenyl sulphide and the latter, methyl ester of 3:5-dinitrosalicylic acid; 3:3'-dicarbophenoxy-4:4'-diacetoxydiphenyl sulphide yields a nitro derivative in which sulphur and the acetoxy groups remain in tact. This nitro compound gives on hydrolysis 3:3'-dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxy-5:5'-dinitrodiphenyl sulphide, and on reduction the corresponding amino derivative with sulphur linkage in tact.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:2'-Dibenzoyl-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl Sulphide—2:2'-Dibenzoyldinaphthyl sulphide (5 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) and nitric acid (*d* 1.4, 25 c.c.) added carefully when a very slow reaction was observed to take place. The mixture soon became red. On being kept overnight, yellow solid separated out which was filtered and crystallised from chloroform, *m. p.* 207°. The same nitro product was obtained by heating the original compound (5 g.) with nitric acid (*d* 1.4, 15 c.c.) till fumes had ceased to evolve and on pouring the product on crushed ice. The nitro compound is soluble in acetic acid and benzene. (Found: C, 66.17; H, 3.20; N, 4.08; S, 5.26. $C_{24}H_{20}O_8N_2S$ requires C, 66.24; H, 3.25; N, 4.55; S, 5.19 per cent).

On hydrolysis with alcoholic potash, it afforded 2:2'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide, *m. p.* 224-25°, identical with the one reported earlier (*loc. cit.*).

On reduction of the nitro compound (5 g.) with zinc dust (7 g.), 95% alcohol (50 c.c.) and ammonium chloride (1 g.) dissolved in water (5 c.c.) after refluxing on a water-bath for 3 hours, a bluish green solution was obtained which gave on dilution a bluish green solid. The solid was heated with cold dilute HCl, stirred, slightly warmed and the blue solid filtered, washed repeatedly with cold chloroform, when a portion dissolved.

The insoluble portion melts at 176-77°. It is soluble in acetone and acetic acid and it is 2:2'-dibenzoyl-6:6'-diaminodiphenyl sulphide. (Found: S, 5.65. $C_{24}H_{24}O_4N_2S$ requires S, 5.75 per cent).

On reduction with granulated tin and concentrated HCl a violet-red solid from alcohol, containing nitrogen and sulphur was obtained, m.p. 192-94°. It is 6-amino-2-naphthol.

3:3'-Dicarbomethoxy-4:4'-dihydroxy-5:5'-dinitrodiphenyl Sulphide.—3:3'-Dicarbomethoxy-4:4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide (5 g.) on similar treatment with nitric acid (d, 1.4, 15 c.c.) and pouring over crushed ice, a product was obtained, which on crystallisation from alcohol yielded one soluble portion of m.p. 124-25° with nitrogen but no sulphur (methyl ester of 3:5-dinitrosalicylic acid) and another insoluble portion (crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 251-52°). (Found: S, 7.42. $C_{17}H_{12}O_{10}N_2S$ requires S, 7.55 per cent).

This compound on hydrolysis yields 3:3'-dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxy-5:5'-dinitrodiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 263-65° and on reduction the corresponding amino compound is obtained.

On similar treatment of 3:3'-dicarbophenoxy-4:4'-diacetoxydiphenyl sulphide with conc. HNO_3 , 3:3'-dicarbophenoxy-4:4'-diacetox-5:5'-dinitrodiphenyl sulphide was obtained; it crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 228-29° (Found: S, 5.14. $C_{20}H_{20}O_{12}N_2S$ requires S, 5.07 per cent). On hydrolysis it also yields 3:3'-dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxy-5:5'-dinitrodiphenyl sulphide. On reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid 3:3'-dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxy-5:5'-diaminodiphenyl sulphide is obtained. In all these reductions tin is removed by passing hydrogen sulphide.